

Appendix 6. Questionnaire

Based on this information:

1. If there were a surge of COVID cases in your area, how likely would you be to wear glasses or recommend wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID?
 - Very likely
 - Likely
 - Unlikely
 - Very unlikely

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements:

2. The decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID was hard for me to make.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
3. I feel I made an informed decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
4. I am satisfied with my decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
5. If there were very few COVID cases in your area, how likely would you be to wear glasses or recommend wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID?
 - Very likely
 - Likely
 - Unlikely
 - Very unlikely

Based on this information:

6. What is the effect of wearing glasses is on your chance of getting COVID?
- Lowers chance a lot
 - Lowers chance a little
 - Has no effect
 - Increases the chance a little
 - Increases the chance a lot
7. How sure are you about the effect of wearing glasses on your chance of getting COVID?
- Very sure
 - Somewhat sure
 - Somewhat unsure
 - Very unsure
8. Which of the following statements is most consistent with the information provided?
Wearing glasses may...
- Reduce the chance of COVID a little
but might reduce it a lot
 - Reduce the chance of COVID a little,
but may have no effect
 - Reduce the chance of COVID a little,
but might increase it a little
 - Increase the chance of COVID it a
little, but might increase it a lot
 - Don't know
9. How likely do you think it is that wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID can cause any important harms?
- Very likely
 - Likely
 - Unlikely
 - Very unlikely
10. How sure are you about whether wearing glasses to reduce COVID can cause important harms?
- Very sure
 - Somewhat sure
 - Somewhat unsure
 - Very unsure

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements:

11. This information is a trustworthy summary of what is known about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

12. This information is a sufficient summary of what is known about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

13. Not enough is known to be sure about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

14. Uncertainty makes me uneasy, anxious, or stressed.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Please indicate what you think about this information:

15. I think the information about whether wearing glasses affects the chance of getting COVID was

- Very clear
- Clear
- Unclear
- Very unclear

16. I think the information about whether wearing glasses to prevent COVID has important harms was

- Very clear
- Clear
- Unclear
- Very unclear

17. Overall, I think the information about wearing glasses to prevent COVID was

- Very helpful
- Helpful
- Unhelpful
- Very unhelpful

18. Say you knew someone who heard that wearing glasses might affect your chance of getting COVID. How likely would you be to share the information you just saw with them?

- Definitely yes
- Probably yes
- Probably no
- Definitely no

Pease answer the following questions about yourself

19. Where do you live?

- Norway
- USA

20. What is your age?

- 18-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55-64 years old
- 65-74 years old

21. What is the highest education level you have completed?

- Some secondary/high school
- Secondary/High school graduate
- Some college or university
- College or university graduate
- Graduate school or professional school graduate

22. How worried are you about getting COVID?

- Extremely worried
- Very worried
- Not very worried
- Not worried

23. How important is it for you to take actions to reduce your chance of getting COVID?

- Extremely important
- Very important
- Not very important
- Not important

Lastly, please answer the following three questions

24. A person taking Drug A has a 1% chance of having an allergic reaction. If 1,000 people take Drug A, how many would you expect to have an allergic reaction?

___ person(s) out of 1,000

25. A person taking Drug B has a 1 in 1,000 chance of an allergic reaction. What percent of people taking Drug B will have an allergic reaction?

___ %

26. Imagine that you flip a coin 1,000 times. What is your best guess about how many times the coin would come up heads in 1,000 flips?

___times out of 1,000